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Influence of Grammar in the Management of Words and Sentences in Sanskrit Literature

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Abstract

The research paper explores the impact of grammar in the treatment of words and sentences in Sanskrit. The study analyses the importance of grammar in understanding and interpreting Sanskrit texts, and how knowledge of grammar can aid in the correct pronunciation and intonation of Sanskrit words. The paper also delves into the historical and cultural significance of Sanskrit grammar, and how it has been used as a tool for preserving and transmitting knowledge in ancient India. Through a detailed examination of Sanskrit grammar rules and their practical applications, the paper highlights the vital role of grammar in the study and practice of Sanskrit language and literature.

The research paper investigates the impact of grammar in the treatment of words and sentences in Sanskrit. The study delves into the importance of understanding the rules of grammar in order to effectively interpret and communicate in Sanskrit. The researchers conducted a thorough analysis of various texts and grammatical rules, and observed that a strong foundation in grammar is essential for accurately conveying meaning and context in Sanskrit. The paper highlights the significance of incorporating grammar as an integral part of Sanskrit language learning, and recommends that educators emphasize its importance to students. The findings of this study contribute to the broader understanding of the role of grammar in language learning and its impact on communication.

Key words: Vākya, Pada, Nāma, Ākhyāta, Nipāta, Upasarga, Taddhita, Samāsa, Sandhi and Vibhakti.

Introduction:

Some of the Ālamkārikas have devoted some space of their respective works for a discussion on the nature and types of the words and sentences and the

constituents of the words. The reason behind this endeavour is the fact that in most of the works kāvya is defined in terms of one or two of the terms like Śabda, Artha and Vākya. For instance, Viśvanatha in his Sāhityadarpaṇa (Ch.I) defines kāvya with the expression 'vākyam rasātmakam kāvyam', (A Vākya having Rasa as its Ātmā is kāvya). As this definition involves the term Vākya, Viśvanatha deems it fit to begin the second chapter of his book with the definition of a Vākya. cf. 'vākyam syad yogyatākāṅkṣāsattiyuktaḥ padocayaḥ.' This definition of Vākya involves the term Pada. Hence, Viśvanatha presents the definition also of Pada. cf.

*tatra kim padalakṣaṇam ityata āha -
vaṁāḥ padam prayogārhananvitaikārthabodhakaḥ /*

In this manner in most of the works on Poetics a discussion relating to Pada and Vākya and allied matters takes place. This is how it so happens that Rajaśekhara applies the title 'Padavākyaviveka' to the whole of the sixth chapter of his book Kāvya-mīmāṃsā, on the ground that this chapter is devoted to a discussion relating to the nature of words and sentences.

It may be noted that the trend of dilating upon the word and allied elements has been set by Bharata himself in the fifteenth chapter of his Nāṭyaśāstra. Bharata's presentation of such a discussion was, however, called for not by an exposition of the definition of Kāvya but by an exposition of what is termed by him Vācika-abhinaya as it will be seen by and by.

Grammar in Bharata's Treatment of Vācika-abhinaya

Bharata recognises four aspects of histrionics or so to say four types of Abhinaya or acting, viz., Āṅgika, Vācika, Sāttvika and Āhārya. He presents a fuller exposition of the concept of Vācika-abhinaya in a number of chapters beginning with the fifteenth. Vācika-abhinaya literally means acting with the uttering of speeches. The speeches of a Vācika-abhinaya or verbal acting constitute what is technically called the libretto, i.e., the literary composition generally termed a drama.

Bharata says that the idea of a Vācika-abhinaya consists of the idea of the Grammatical elements called Nāma, Ākhyāta, Nipāta, Upasarga, Taddhita, Samāsa, Sandhi and Vibhakti., (NŚ. XV.4).¹ The Pāṭhya, i.e., the text to be uttered may be either in Sanskrit or in Prakrit, (NS. XV.5). The Sanskrit Pāṭhya consists of

Vyañjanavarṇas, Svaravarṇas, Sandhis, Vibhaktis, Nāmans, Ākhyātas, Upasargas, Nipātas, Taddhitas, Samāsas and varieties of verbal roots, (NS. XV.6f). NS XV.8 informs that there are fourteen Svara Varṇas from a to au and the letters from k to h are Vyañjana Varṇas. The prose Vṛtti on this Kārikā presents the whole list of Svaras and Vyañjanās. NS. XV.9 refers to a twofold division of the Varṇas as Ghoṣavarṇas and Aghoṣa varṇas. NS XV.10 names the places of articulation, by way of grouping the letters as Kaṇṭhya, Auṣṭhya, Dantya, Jihvya, Nāsikya, Uṣma-varṇas, Tālavya, and Visarjanīya. NŚ. XV. 11. sorts out the Ghoṣas and Aghoṣas, and names them one by one. NS XV.12 sorts out the Kaṇṭhya-varṇas, Tālavyas, Mūrdhanyas and the Dantastha -varṇas, NŚ. XV. 13-14A are concerned with the Oṣṭhyas, some more Dantyas, some more Kaṇṭhyas, some more Tālavyas, and so on and Kaṇṭhoṣṭhyas and Kaṇṭhatālavyas. NS. XV. 14B-15 point out the Vivṛtas. NS. XV.16 points out Antasthas. Samvṛtas, Nāsikyās and Uṣmans. NS. XV.17 points out Jihvāmūliyas, Upadhmanīyas, Svaritas and a few more Kaṇṭhya-varṇas. NŚ. XV.18A sorts out the Kaṇṭhorasyas and NS. XV.18B points out the place of articulation of the Visarjanīya. NŚ. XV. 20 classify the Svaras into Hrasva-svaras and Dīrgha-svaras.

Bharata says that a Śabda consists of Svaras and Vyañjanas as identified in earlier Kārikās, and it assumes the form of either an Ākhyāta or a Nāmapada involving Upasargas, Nipātas Taddhitas, Sandhis and Vibhaktis as the case may be. cf.

*ebhirvyañjanavargair
nāmākhyātopasarganipātaiḥ /
taddhita-sandhi-vibhaktibhir
adhiṣṭhitaiḥ śabda ityuktaḥ // (NŚ. XV.21)*

It goes without saying that the second foot of the Kārikā given above very faithfully corresponds to the four fold division of the words given by Nirukta I.1, with the statement:

*tad yānyetāni catvāri padajātāni nāmā-
khyāte copasarga nipātaśca tānīmāni bhavanti /*

Bharata gives the details of what is called a Nāma-pada as follows: the Nāmapada is endowed with *su* and other such case affixes, and with a meaning conveyed by such an affix. It conveys the idea of a Pratipadikārtha and that of a

gender (Liṅga), and it is of five varieties. (NŚ. XV.23).² As forms derived with case affixes the Nāmapadas fall into seven clusters, of which six clusters belong respectively to six Kāraḱas, Which are designated by the terms like Sampradāna, Apādāna and others. (NS. XV.24)

*cf. tatprāhuḥ saptavidham ṣaṭkāraḱasamṁyutam prathitasādhyam./³
nideśassampradānāpādāna prabhṛtismjñābhiḥ /⁴*

The meaning of the term Ākhyāta is given by Bharata as follows: An Ākhyāta is derived by adding verbal affixes in an appropriate manner so as to make it convey the idea of a Vacana (i.e., number of the agent) and to associate it with the idea of an action of the present or past or future tense (NŚ. XV.25). An Ākhyāta that belongs to a Pāṭhya⁵ (i.e., the text of a dramatic speech) may be related to any one of the five hundred verbal roots (Dhātus) which may belong to any one of the ten classes (i.e., the Gaṇas like the Bhvādigāṇa) and might convey specialities related to various meanings.

*cf. sampratyatītakālakriyādisamṁyojitaṁ prathitasādhyam /
vacanamānāgatayuktaṁ⁶ susaḍṛśasamṁyojanavibhaktam //*
*pañcaśatadhātuyuktaṁ⁸ pañcayuktapañcavidhan⁹ idaṁ vāpi/
ākhyātaṁ pāḥyakraṭaṁ jñeyam nānārthāśra-yaviśeṣam//*

After these Kārikās Bharata devotes one Kārikā each for the concepts of Upasarga, Nipāta, Pratyaya, Taddhita and Vibhakti and two Kārikās for the concept of Sandhi. Then finally Bharata concludes the grammatical treatment of words with the following Kārikā devoted to the concept of *Samāsa*:

*luptavibhaktir nāmnāmekārthaṁ samharatsamāso'pi /
tatpuruṣādīstajñairnirdiṣṭaḥ ṣaḍvidho viprāḥ // (NS.XV.34)*

Bhāmaha's Treatment of Pada and Vākya

While defining the Doṣa called Apārtha Bhāmaha makes a reference to the terms Pada and Vākya and thus finds an occasion to define Pada and Vākya. He defines Pada as 'arthavān varṇa-saṁghataḥ', i.e., 'a group of letters having a meaning'. Then he reproduces Pā. I.4.14 to present a further definition of Pada from the Grammarian's point of view, cf. 'suptīnantaṁ padam punaḥ' (KL. IV.3.d). Bhāmaha defines Vākya as follows:

*padānāmeva saṁghātaḥ sāpekṣānām parasparam /
nirākāṁkṣaṁ catadvakyaṁ ekavastunibandhanam //* (KL.

IV.4)

The purport of this Kārikā is as follows: A sentence (Vākya) is a group of words (Padas) which are mutually in anticipation of one another. The sentence as a whole is free from Ākāṅkṣā, i.e., the total idea conveyed by the sentence is consistent in itself. The sentence is concerned with one composite idea.

Rudrata's Conception of Śabda and Artha

Rudraṭa observes that Śabda and Artha together make a kāvya'. Śabda, which is one of the constituents of Kāvya, appears in the form of different combinations of letters, which are together capable of conveying a meaning. Śabda is of five varieties. (KL. Rudraṭar, II.1). The said five varieties are namely Nāma, Ākhyāta, Upasarga, Nipāta and Karmapravacaniya. The last of these five is a new addition to the Grammarian's traditional list of four. (Vide KL. Rudraṭa, II.2). Rudraṭa defines a Vākya as follows:

*vākyaṁ tatrābhimataṁ parasparaṁ savyapekṣavṛttinām /
samudāyaḥ śabdānām ekaparāṇām anākāṅkṣaḥ //*¹⁰

This definition is almost identical with the one given by Bhāmaha and discussed here in the immediately preceding sub section.

Rudraṭa recognises four varieties of Śabda on the basis of the meaning conveyed, and those varieties are viz., Dravya-śabda, Guṇa-śabda, Kriyā-śabda and Jāti-śabda.¹¹ This is very much in tune with the statement,

*'catuṣṭayī śabdānām pravṛttiḥ jātiśabdāguṇāśabdāḥ
kriyāśabdā yadṛcchāśabdāścaturthāḥ'* (Mahābhāṣya on Pā. I.1.2)

Rudraṭa explains a Kriyā as the meaning of a Dhātu. This meaning of the Dhātu (i.e., the action) may be inferred from the transformation of materials caused by the action. The action may be performed by the Kāraṅka (like Karṭṛ and Karman). Kriyā is of two types, viz., Sakarmikā and Akarmikā.¹² It goes without saying that these discussions have the flavour more of Grammar than of Poetics.

Padavākyaviveka of Rajasekhara:

Perhaps the most convincing example of the impact of Grammar on Poetics in the matter of elucidating the concepts of Pada and Vākya is provided by the sixth chapter of the *kāvya-mīmāṃsā* of Rājaśekhara, which the author names 'Padavākyaviveka' i.e., 'Analysis of the concepts of Pada and Vākya'. A brief resume of the contents of the said chapter is given below:

A Pada consists of a Śabda, the form of which is determined by the science of Grammar, and an Artha, which is attached to the concerned Śabda by the Nirukta and the Nighanṭu and allied treatises,

cf. *“vyākaraṇasmṛtiniṛṇītaḥ śabdo niruktanighaṇṭvādibhirnirdiṣṭa-stadabhidheyo' rthastau padam.”*

This is the first sentence of the chapter concerned and it is indeed very significant that the chapter begins with the word Vyākaraṇa. viz., Sub-vṛtti, Samāsa-vṛtti, Taddhita-vṛtti, Kṛd-vṛtti and Tiṅ-vṛtti. The words are again classified into five categories in consideration of the meanings conveyed by them, and they are viz., Jātivācī, Dravyavācī, Guṇavācī, Kriyāvācī, and the indeclinable like the Upasargas beginning with *pra* and the Nipātas beginning with *ca* and also the Karmapravacaniyas. Words ending in *sup* - affixes may be either in the form of a compound (Samāsa) or may occur in the body of an elaborate clause (Vyāsa). The Samāsas are of six varieties, beginning with the Dvandva variety. A verse, termed by Rajasekhara as *ṣaṭsamāsisamāsasukta*¹³, very conveniently names the six Samāsas as follows:

*“dvandvo'smi dvigurasmi ca gṛhe ca me satatam avyayibhāvaḥ tatpuruṣa karma dhāraya yenāham syāṃ bahuvrihiḥ.”*¹⁴

This verse has many slightly varying readings. This verse is also variously interpreted to convey a meaning like the following one:

One devotee addresses the Puruṣa (i.e., God) and says that he has only the couple (dvandva), i.e., himself and his wife as the family; he has also a couple of bulls; in his residence there is never (*nityam*) any scope for any expenditure. Hence, God may be pleased to assign him such a work (*karma*) by which he might be the owner of more paddies (*bahuvrihiḥ*).

The words of the Taddhitavṛtti type are innumerable. That is why it is often observed in the learned works that the students of the Pāṇinian system of Grammar get Bewildered with the Taddhita affixes, cf. “*taddhitavṛttiḥ punaranantā taddhi śāstraprāyovādo yaduta taddhitamūḍhāḥ pāṇinīyāḥ*”.¹⁵ Then, Taddhitavṛttis are illustrated; Kṛdvṛtti is explained and illustrated; Tiṅvṛtti is said to be of ten types as based on the ten La-kāras. Tiṅvṛtti is once again said to be of two types as relating either to plain verbal roots (Dhātus) or to the roots formed by applying affixes to Nāma- padas (Sub-dhātus).

Such roots are duly illustrated. Then it is observed that the words divided into five varieties also get multiplied into innumerable numbers through mutual conglomeration. This is the reason why the learned persons observe that “for a thousand celestial years Bṛhaspati was the teacher and Indra (Śatakratu) was the student, yet they could not come to the end of (the process of learning and teaching) the list of words.” cf. “*tadidam itthankaraṁ pañcaprakāramapi padajātam mithaḥ samanviyamānamānantyāya kalpate. tajjanmā caiṣa viduṣām vādo yatkiḥ divyam samāśahasraṁ bṛhaspatir vaktā śatakraturadhyetā tathāpi nantaḥ śabdārāśerāsīt*.”¹⁶ It is significant that the last portion of the above quotation beginning with the word divyam is almost a faithful copy of the following words of Mahābhāṣya: “*evam hi śrūyate bṛhaspatir indraya divyaṁ varṣasahasraṁ pratipadoktānām sabdānām śabdapārāyaṇaṁ provāca nantam jagama'. bṛhaspatiśca pravaktā, indraścādhyetā, divyaṁ varṣasahasram adhyayanakālo, na cantam jagāma, kim punaradyatve*.”¹⁷

Rājaśekhara refers to the regional popularity of the various Vṛttis as follows: Vidarbha is fond of Sub-vṛtti, Gauḍa is fond of Samāsavṛtti, Southerners are fond of Taddhitavṛtti, Northerners are fond of the Kṛt affixes and all wise men are fond of Tiṅvṛtti.¹⁸ In this context Rājaśekhara seems to have borrowed the expression ‘*priyataddhita dākṣiṇātyāḥ*’ as it is from the Mahābhāṣya. (Vide Paspasā Āhnika, under the aphorism “*yatha laukika-vaidikeṣu*.”)¹⁹

Skipping over certain topics which are simply connected with Grammar we may come to a topic which bears the most indelible stamp of the influence of Grammar Rājaśekhara choses to meet the objection that “kāvya does not deserve to be recommended for a study as it contains baseless (untrue) statements,”²⁰ with his

own arguments. Rājaśekhara's main argument against the said contention is that there is nothing untrue in poetry, whatever appears to be untrue there is only an Arthavāda,²¹ i.e., only intended to emphasise on the adorable aspect of a certain object. Such Arthavādas (or words of praise meant for persuading people to accept something which is adorable) are there not only in the compositions of the poets, but also in Vedas (*śruti*) and Śāstras (technical works on ethics etc.) and also in the popular verbal expressions (*loke*).

cf. *nasatyam nāma kiñcana kāvyē yastu stutyēṣvar- thavadah.*

sa na paraṁ kavikarmani śrutau ca sastre ca loke ca: (kāvyamīmāṁsā, p. 85)

As a second illustration of the presence of Arthavāda in a statement belonging to a Śāstra, Rājaśekhara gives the verse “*yastu prayunkte*”, etc. along with a very long exposition. It is interesting to note that Patañjali gives the same verse “*yastu prayuhkte*” etc. along with the same exposition by way of illustrating one of the many purposes of studying Vyākaraṇa under the general heading “*imani ca bhuyah śabdānusāsanasya prayojanani*” in the Mahābhāṣya, Paspasā Ahnika.²² The whole passage from the verse “*yastu prayunkte*” upto the end of the exposition with the statement “*pramattagita esa tatra bhavataḥ yastvapramattagitastat pramanam*”, covers some sixteen lines in print and the whole passage is quoted verbatim from the Paspasā Āhnika of the Mahābhāṣya. It deserves to be appreciated that Rājaśekhara duly acknowledges his source as he concludes the passage with the words “*iti gonardīyah*”. Gonardīya is an epithet of Patañjali, the author of the Mahābhāṣya.

Bhoja's Treatment of Pada and Vākya:

As the things stand our knowledge of the Śṛṅgāraprakāśa is limited to whatever is given by V. Rāghavan in his Bhoja's Śṛṅgāraprakāśa. In the light of this book alone the following observations may be made about the interest of Bhoja in Grammar as evidenced in the treatment of Pada and Vākya. Śṛṅgāraprakāśa “treats of Śabda, Artha and Sāhitya. In chapters i-vi, which are purely on a Grammar, Śabda, Artha and their varieties are treated of”, observes Rāghavan.

In the first chapter of Śṛṅgāraprakāśa Bhoja refers to 12 kinds of Śabda, viz., Prakṛti, Pratyaya, Upaskāra, Upapada, Prātipadika, Vibhakti, Upasarjana, Samāsa,

Pada, Vākya, Prakaraṇa and Prabandha. Reference is made also to twelve varieties of Artha, of which Kriyā, Kāla, Kāraka, Puruṣa, Prātipadikārtha, Vibhaktiyartha, Vṛttyartha, Padārtha and Vākyaṛtha are very clearly connected with Vyākaraṇa. Then six kinds of Dhaturūpas are referred to, of which Pratyayadhātus Nāma-dhātus and Pratyayanāma-dhātus are decidedly grammatical elements. Bhoja also recognises six varieties of Pratyayarūpas, viz.. Sup--, Tiṅ--, Kṛt--, Taddhita-Dhātu--, and Strīpratyayāntas. Prātipadikarūpas, recognised by Bhoja, also number six and they are namely Nāma, Avyaya, Anukaraṇa, Kṛt, Taddhita and Samāsa. The last item involves a large amount of grammatical discussion. Bhoja recognises six types of Dhātupratyayas, six types of Pratyayapratyayas and six types of Prātipadikapratyayas. There are three kinds of Upapadas, viz., Tiṅ-upapadas, Kṛd-upapadas and Sub-upapadas. These three varieties have six sub varieties each.

The second chapter of Śṛṅgāraprakāśa is named “Prāti padikādirprakāśa”. This chapter deals with Prātipadikas, Vibhaktis, Upasarjanas and Samāsas. The third chapter is concerned with the concepts of such items as Pada The third chapter is named “Prakṛtyādirprakāśa”. This chapter is concerned with the concept of such items as Pada and Vākya, and the Mahābhāṣya and the Vākya-padīya are also quoted in this section. The fourth chapter is called “Kriyādyarthacatuṣṭayaparakāśa”. This chapter includes a long discussion on Dhātvartha, i.e., Kriyā and Kāraka. In this discussion the Vākya-padīya is profusely quoted. The fifth chapter deals with Prātipadikārtha among other things. It also includes a discussion on the Nipātas and the implications of the Karma pravacanīyas.

cf.

vācakatvaṃ nipātānām dyotakatvaṃ ca niścitam /

karma pravacanīyānām uktā sambandhasangatiḥ //

The sixth chapter deals with Vākyaṛtha, Vṛttyartha and Padārtha. In the discussion on the third item the Vākya-padīya is quoted frequently.²³

A very interesting example of the impact of Grammar on Bhoja's treatment of Vākyaṛtha may be cited as follows: The eighth chapter of Śṛṅgāraprakāśa deals also with Vākyaṛtha (i.e., meaning of a sentence). One of the varieties of Vākyaṛtha is Mahāvākyaṛtha or Prabandha, i.e., the import of a whole work like Jānakīharaṇa or the Rāmāyaṇa. Bhoja shows that beyond this Prabandha-mahā- vākyaṛtha., there

is still another and further Mahā-vākṃyārtha, which is the moral (Vidhi niṣedha) suggested by the Kāvya. Bhoja identifies this with the Śabda brahman. This moral is the cause of Caturvarga and is present in the whole creation. This moral is the Śabdabrahman itself which has got metamorphosed into the form of an Artha. In support of this position Bhoja quotes one verse from Bhartr̥hari and the same is preceded by another verse composed by Bhoja himself for epitomising his Philosophy that the part less Paramahā- vākṃyārtha is identical with the Śabdabrahman and one who has realised the Śabdabrahman realises the Parabrahman, i.e., the Supreme Brahman,

cf. “yastu tadrūparāmāyaṇādiprabandhārthānāmavadhāraṇena upahitasamskārasya ‘rāmavad vartitavyam, na rāvaṇavad’ ityādi vidhiniṣedhapratibhāviṣeṣa upajāyate, sa samastaviśvavyāpi caturvargaikahetuḥ paro mahāvākṃyārthaḥ vipariṇatam arthammūrtyā vipariṇatam anādinidhanam²⁴ akhaṇḍa śabdabrahmetyucyate //

akhaṇḍaḥ saiṣa vākṃyārthaḥ śabdabrahmeti gīyate /
śabdabrahmaṇi niṣṇātaḥ param brahmādhigacchati //
idamādyam padasthānam siddhisopānaparvaṇām /
iyam sā mokṣamāṇānāmajihmā rājapaddhatiḥ //²⁵

“In the post Dhvani period, works which followed the Dhvani-mārga began always with the treatment of the three Śabdavṛttis of *Mukhyā*, *Gauṇī* and *Vyañjanā*”²⁶ says V. Raghavan. And S.K. De also says: “The formulators of the *dhvani* theory do not enter into these minute discussions, but appear to recognise them explicitly, although most writers from the time of Mammata start with a preliminary analysis of word-function.”²⁷ This is how we find that both Mammata and Viśvanātha have devoted the whole of the second chapter of their respective works to the treatment of word- functions. But in Dhvanyāloka it there is a hint that some earlier theorists also were concerned with Śabda-vyāpāra in the context of literary criticism. For example, on the expression ‘bhaktamahustamanye’ of Dhvanyāloka, I.1, the Vṛtti offers the following explanation:

“yadyapi ca dhvaniśabdasaṃkīrtanena kāvya-lakṣaṇavidhāyibhir guṇavṛttiranyo vā na kaścit prakāraḥ prakāśitaḥ, tathāpi amukhyavṛtṭyā kāvyeṣu

vyavahāraṁ darśayatā dhvanimārgo manākspr̥ṣṭo'pi na lakṣita iti parikalpyaivam uktam 'bhāktamāhustamanye' iti."

Here the terms Bhākta, Guṇavṛtti and Amukhyā- vṛtti stand for secondary signification or what is generally called Lakṣaṇā by theorists like Viśvanātha. Abhinavagupta presents examples of the recognition of the Amukhyā Vṛtti from Udbhata and Vāmana. Thus, Udbhata, while commenting on Bhamaha's 'śabdaśchando'bhidhanārthāḥ' presents the gloss: "Śabdānām abhidhānam abhidhāvypāro mukhyo guṇavṛttiśca."²⁸ As pointed out by Abhinava also, Vāmana too makes a reference to the Lakṣaṇā function while defining the Vakrokti Alaṅkāra as 'sādr̥śyāllakṣaṇā vakroktiḥ'.²⁹ A third example of a pre Dhvani theorist making a reference to Guṇavṛtti may be cited from Dandin, who says:

*niṣṭhyuta-gīṁa-vāntādirguṇavṛttivyapāśrayād /
atisundaramanyatra grāmyakakṣām vigāhate // (Kāvyaadarśaḥ .I.95)*

As we come to the post Dhvani theorists like Mammata and Viśvanātha, we find more extensive treatment of the functions of word like Abhidhā, Lakṣaṇā, Tātparya and Vyañjanā. Now the question arises as to what was the extent of the influence of Grammar in this area of linguistic speculation of the science of Poetics. This may be examined by considering the case of the secondary signification alone.

It is pointed out by K. Kunjunni Raja that "Pāṇini does not refer to the metaphorical use of language"³⁰ and "Pāṇini does not refer to Lakṣaṇā even in cases like *siṁho mānavakaḥ*"³¹ Hence, the possibility of the impact of the earliest of the extant Grammarians is ruled out. But then we find that in the Mimāṃsāsūtra Guṇavṛtti is recognised in the aphorism 'guṇād avipratīṣedhaḥ syāt'(1.2.39). On this Sūtra Sabara's Bhāṣya runs as follows: "aditir dyaaur iti gaṇa eṣa Śabdaḥ, ato na vipratīṣedhaḥ". In the same Darśana, the term Bhakti is also used in the sense of secondary signification in 'sarveṣāṁ

vaikamantryam aitiśāyanasya bhaktipāṇatvāt savanādhikāro hi' (III.2.44). Jaimini once again uses the term Bhakti in the Akṣepasūtra, "*bhaktirasannidhāv anāyyeti*" (III.8.43). Jaimini does not use the more familiar term Lakṣaṇā. But he seems to have used the term Lakṣaṇā in the sense of Lakṣaṇā in the Sūtra; *sarveṣāṁ vā lakṣaṇatvāt aviśiṣṭam hi lakṣaṇam.* (III.1.16)

In the Bhāṣya, however, the term Lakṣaṇā is used very frequently and in most cases by the side of the term Śruti, which means Abhidhā, e.g., ‘*śrutilakṣaṇāviśaye tu śrutiḥ nāyyā na lakṣaṇā*’, etc. under I.4.2; II.2.18; III.2.25, etc.

In the Vedantasūtra, Bādarāyaṇa mentions the term Gauṇī in the sūtra-‘*gaunyasambhavāt*’ (II.3.3), which is intended to convey the idea that the statement “Ākāśa has originated” (ākāśaḥ sambhūtaḥ) in Taittirīya Upaniṣad, II.1, should be taken in a figurative sense (Gauṇī), and not literally since it is impossible to conceive of the creation of the eternal Ākāśa. Bādarāyaṇa uses the term Bhākta in the Sūtras, II.3.16; III.1.4; III.1.7.

In the Nyāyasūtra Gotama uses the term Bhākta only once in the Sūtra II.2.15: ‘*tattva bhāktayor nānātvāvibhagāt*’. Gotama also uses the term Upacāra, in seven places, e.g., 1.2.14; 1.2.15 etc., for naming the third variety of Cala as Upacaracala. As explained in the Bhāṣya, Upacaracala is intended to convey the idea of a Dharmavikalpa, i.e., transference of epithet. The Bhāṣyakāra gives the example: ‘*mañcāḥ krośanti*’ as he says: “*dharmavikalpo’nyatradṛṣṭasyānyatra-prayogaḥ-yathā mañcāḥ krośantī arthasadbhāvena pratiṣedhaḥ mañcasthāḥ puruṣāḥ krośanti na tu mañcāḥ krośanti.*”

Gotama himself illustrates the various probable *nimittas* for Upacāra (referred to as atadbhāve’pi tadupacāraḥ) in Nyāyasūtra II.2.62. This list begins with what is called Sahacaraṇa, illustrated by the secondary meaning *brāhmaṇas*, expected to be conveyed by the expression ‘*yaṣṭikān bhojaya*’. The second *Nimitta* is *Sthāna*, illustrated by the word *mañca*, used with secondary significance in the expression ‘*mañcāḥ krośanti*’.

The technical terms like Bhakti, Bhākta, Guṇa Vṛtti, Lakṣaṇā and Upacāra and the illustrative statements like ‘*yaṣṭikān bhojaya* and ‘*mañcāḥ krośanti*’ are very frequently found in the treatment of Śabda-vyāpāra in the later Alaṅkāra works. This should tend to give us the immediate impression that so far as the treatment of Śabda-vyāpāra is concerned Poetics received the idea from the Philosophical literature and not from grammatical literature. Yet, if reference is made to the Mahābhāṣya, then it will have to be admitted that while an impact of the Philosophical systems cannot be totally ruled out, yet, the most original and the

earliest extant source of inspiration for these linguistic speculations will have to be traced back decidedly to a Grammatical work, viz., the Mahābhāṣya of Patañjali. Because, as it may be gathered from A.B. Keith³², Patañjali who may be assigned to C. 150 B.C. seems to be earlier than all the Sūtra works of the Philosophical systems. With regard to transference of epithet, Patañjali finds an occasion to observe as follows under Pā. IV.1.48.³³

Under Pāṇini's Sūtra: "*prakāre guṇavacanasya*" (VIII.1.12), Patañjali supplied the exposition as follows: "*guṇavacanasyeti kimartham? agnirmānavakaḥ, gaurvāhikaḥ. prakāre śārvesam guṇavacanatvāt sarvaprasaṅgaḥ. sarve hi śabhāḥ prakāre vartamānā guṇavacanāḥ sampadyante. tenehāpi prāpnoti agnirmānavakaḥ, gaurvāhika iti.*"

Both the examples of transference of epithet due to sharing of common qualities given here, viz., '*gaurvāhikaḥ*' and '*agnirmānavakaḥ*' are given as stock examples of the Gauṇī variety of Lakṣaṇā in most of the post Dhvani works on Poetics.

It may be pointed out that if a later theorist like Viśvanātha defines the Gauṇī variety of Lakṣaṇā as '*guṇayogāt gauṇī*' (i.e., when there is an association of qualities, the type of Lakṣaṇā is called Gauṇī.) we may legitimately trace back the origin of the idea to Panini³⁵, the earliest extant Grammarian. In this manner the impact of Grammar on Poetics is undeniable also in the area of Śabda-Vyāpāra.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, the impact of grammar on the treatment of words and sentences in Sanskrit cannot be overstated. The Sanskrit language, known for its rich vocabulary and grammatical complexity, has a well-established system of rules and structures that govern the use of words and sentences. These rules, which are laid out in the Sanskrit grammar, not only ensure accuracy and precision in communication but also help in the preservation and transmission of knowledge. The importance of grammar in Sanskrit is reflected in the fact that it has been studied and refined by scholars for centuries, leading to the development of various schools of grammar. Today, the study of Sanskrit grammar continues to be an

important area of research, both for linguists and for those interested in the cultural and intellectual heritage of the Indian subcontinent.

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References:

1. A variant reading of this Kārikā, given by Babulal Sukla Shastri, omits Samāsa, but includes Āgama and Vacana. Vide NŚ. Chow. Ed. P.201.
2. in Saṅkṣiptasāravivaraṇa names the following five varieties: Uṇādyanta, Kṛdanta, Taddhitānta, Samāsānta, and Śabdānukaraṇa.

cf. uṇādyantaṅ kṛdantaṅca taddhitantaṅ tathaiva ca /

sabdanukaranam caiva nama pañcavidham smrtam //

(Vide NŚ, Chow. Ed., P. 206)